

Formation Constants and IR Spectrum of Zinc(II) Mandelate

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The stepwise formation constants of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes of Zn(II) with mandelic acid have been determined in aqueous solution employing Bjerrum's method. The $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$, and $\log \beta_2$ values have been found to be 2.68, 2.32, and 5.00 respectively, at $30^\circ \pm 0.2^\circ$. The IR spectrum of the isolated complex (1 : 2) suggests that the chelation has taken place involving coordination of both, hydroxyl and carboxyl, groups of the mandelate ions.

IN continuation of our previous work^{1,2}, the present attempt has been made to study the stepwise formation constants of Zn(II)-mandelate complex. The bonding in the complex has been discussed on the basis of its (1 : 2) IR spectrum.

Experimental

All chemicals were either of B.D.H. 'AnalaR' or equivalent quality.

Standard solutions of the ligand and the metal salt were prepared in double-distilled water.

For pH-measurements 'Polymetron CL-41' pH-meter was employed.

IR spectrum was obtained with the help of 'Perkin Elmer Infrared Spectrophotometer 237'.

Results and Discussion

The interaction of Zn(II) ions with mandelic acid has caused considerable lowering of pH. A pH-metric titration of 1 : 1 metal-ligand system with alkali has revealed an inflection at one equivalent of alkali. This indicates that only carboxylic protons of mandelic acid are liberated during chelation. The chelation reaction may be represented as :

pH-metric titrations of 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 mixtures of Zn(II) and mandelic acid with alkali show inflection at two equivalents of alkali. This corresponds to the formation of 1 : 2 complex only, as represented by the following equation :

The stepwise formation constants of these 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes were determined by Bjerrum's method³. The aqueous solutions containing perchloric acid plus ligand, and perchloric acid plus ligand plus metal salt solution, of constant volume

(50.0 ml) and of constant ionic strength (0.1 M NaClO₄) were titrated against standard alkali at a temperature of $30^\circ \pm 0.2^\circ$. The pK_a values of the ligand, (3.36), as reported by Khadikar⁴ under the same experimental conditions, was employed for the calculation of the formation constants of Zn(II)-mandelate complexes.

In calculating \bar{n} and [A⁻] the concentrations were corrected for changes in volume produced by the addition of alkali during titrations. A series of values of \bar{n} and [A⁻] corresponding to different values of pH were calculated (Table 1) and the formation curve obtained by plotting \bar{n} values against p[A⁻], (Fig. 1).

Fig 1. Formation Curve Zn(II) Mandelate

The values of \bar{n} after pH 4.25 are almost constant (≈ 2.20). This indicates that under the experimental conditions used, only 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes are formed between Zn(II) and mandelic acid. From the formation curve the values of $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$, and $\log \beta_2$ are found to be 2.68, 2.32, and 5.00 respectively. The standard deviations of the values of $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$, and $\log \beta_2$ are found to be ± 0.05 , ± 0.05 , and ± 0.10 respectively.

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Fig. 2. IR Spectra Zn(II) Mandelate—Mandelic Acid...

IR spectra of the isolated complex $Zn(C_8H_7O_3)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ and mandelic acid were obtained in the region $4000-650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ by KBr disc technique (Fig. 2). Mandelic acid shows sharp peaks at 680, 720, 840, 870, 1020, 1180, 1280, 1430, 1490, 1702, 2958, and 3420 cm^{-1} and the complex at 685, 1000, 1190, 1245, 1270, 1335, 1360, 1400, and 1590 cm^{-1} and a broad band at $3220-3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ with a peak at 3260 cm^{-1} .

There is a considerable shift in the OH group frequency from 3420 cm^{-1} in mandelic acid to 3260 cm^{-1} in the complex. The ionised carboxyl group stretching frequency is also found to have been shifted to 1590 cm^{-1} (ligand 1702 cm^{-1}). This suggests that the chelation has taken place involving coordination of both, hydroxyl and carboxyl, groups of the mandelic acid.

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF ZN(II)-MANDELATE

pH	\bar{n}	V_t	[HA] $\times 10^3$	[A ⁻] $\times 10^3$	$p[A^-]$
2.65	0.16	50.5ml	7.92	1.37	2.863
2.70	0.26	50.9	7.85	1.54	2.812
2.80	0.42	52.0	7.72	1.89	2.723
3.00	0.78	54.0	7.40	2.87	2.542
3.40	1.66	57.4	6.95	6.80	2.167
3.65	2.00	58.5	6.85	11.82	1.928
3.85	2.15	59.8	6.69	18.40	1.735
4.00	2.22	60.4	6.62	25.70	1.590
4.25	2.25	61.2	6.53	45.20	1.345

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